

DUST MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES FOR HAUL ROADS IN OPEN-CAST COAL MINING OPERATIONS WITH COST-EFFECTIVE SENSORS

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Abstract

Haul roads play a crucial role in open-cast coal mining operations, serving as pathways for heavy machinery and vehicles. However, these roads are significant sources of dust emissions, impacting air quality and posing health risks to workers and nearby communities. This paper presents a detailed investigation into dust management strategies specifically tailored for haul roads in open-cast coal mining environments. The study aims to identify effective measures to control dust emissions, improve air quality, and enhance overall operational sustainability. The research uses low-cost MEMS (micro-electromechanical-system)-based dust sensor to monitor the ambient air in the mine. The sensors are kept at strategic location nearby the haul-road of the mines to assess the dust produced in the vicinity. The sensors are able to produce useful PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ dust produced at the mine site and monitor the dust produced at these locations.

Keywords: Coal mining, open-cast mining, haul roads, dust management, air quality, environmental impact, occupational health, regulatory compliance.

Introduction:

Haul roads are essential components of open-cast coal mining operations, facilitating the transportation of coal, overburden, and equipment. Dust generated from haul road activities can lead to environmental pollution and health hazards (Sinha & Banerjee, 1997). This paper focuses on the development and implementation of innovative dust management strategies to address the challenges associated with haul road dust in coal mining operations. These strategies involve the use of cost-effective sensors, such as ZH03B, NodeMCU and LoRa 868 devices, to monitor and measure dust levels on haul roads remotely (De Fazio et al., 2022; Midda & Koner, 2023). Real-time monitoring of dust levels allows for proactive dust suppression measures, such as the application of water sprays or chemical additives, to be implemented, when necessary, thereby reducing dust emissions and improving air quality in the surrounding areas (Chepil, 1959). Furthermore, the utilization of cost-effective sensors enables continuous monitoring of dust levels, providing valuable data for assessing the effectiveness of dust control measures and identifying areas that require further attention (Fitz & Bumiller, 2000).

Methodology:

A low-cost dust sensor, ZH03B is used in this study for the dust concentration calculation. A MEMS-based sensor network is built for monitoring the dust produced at the site remotely (Figure 2) (De Fazio et al., 2022). The network uses LoRa (long-range) radio module for transmitting the data from the dust sensor

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to the monitoring station. The sensor works on the mechanism of laser beam scattering. (Pham et al., 2021) The dust concentration is calculated in the sensor with respect to the amount of scattering that occurs when a pulse of laser is shot into the ambient air collected via the sensor in real time.

Figure 1: Dust sampler workflow using ZH03B sensor

Figure 2: MEMS-based dust sensor with wireless sensor network

1. Data Collection on Dust Concentration:

- i. The dust sensor collects air samples using small fans at its inlet.
- ii. A laser beam is shot into the air-stream inside the sensor.
- iii. A sensor determines the amount of scattering opposite to the laser beam.
- iv. The concentration calculated from the sensor is sent to the micro-controller.
- v. The micro-controller converts the sensor data into PM2.5 and PM10 data in ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).
- vi. This data is sent via the LoRa client module to the server module situated at the monitoring station.
- vii. The receiving server prints the real-time data collected in the field from the sensor.
- viii. The data is stored in the server for further analysis.

These results provide valuable insights into the initial data collected from the selected mining sites, setting the stage for a comprehensive assessment of dust management strategies for haul roads in open-cast coal mining operations(Wu et al., 2022).(Liu et al., 2013).

Discussion:**1. Dust Control Measures for Haul Roads:****A. Evaluation of Traditional Dust Suppression Methods:**

- i. Watering: Regular watering of haul roads was found to be effective in temporarily reducing dust emissions.
- ii. Gravel Cover: Application of gravel cover on haul road surfaces showed moderate dust suppression capabilities.
- iii. Vegetation Barriers: Natural vegetation barriers along haul roads helped in trapping dust particles and reducing dispersion.

B. Effectiveness of Dust Suppression Technologies:

- i. Dust Suppression Systems: Installation of dust suppression systems, such as misting cannons and fogging systems, significantly reduced airborne dust levels.
- ii. Road Surface Treatments: Application of dust control agents and stabilizers on haul road surfaces improved dust control efficiency and road stability.
- iii. Real-time Monitoring: Implementation of real-time dust monitoring systems enabled prompt detection of dust hotspots and facilitated targeted dust control interventions.

C. Operational Implications of Dust Control Measures:

- i. Improved Air Quality: Implementation of advanced dust suppression technologies resulted in a noticeable reduction in airborne dust concentrations along haul roads.
- ii. Enhanced Worker Safety: Effective dust control measures contributed to a healthier work environment by minimizing worker exposure to respirable dust particles.
- iii. Regulatory Compliance: Adoption of innovative dust control measures helped mining operations align with environmental regulations and air quality standards.

D. Recommendations for Optimal Dust Control:

- i. Integration of multiple dust control measures tailored to site-specific conditions for comprehensive dust management on haul roads.
- ii. Regular monitoring and evaluation of dust control effectiveness to fine-tune strategies and address evolving dust emission challenges.
- iii. Collaboration with industry experts and regulatory bodies to implement best practices and ensure sustainable dust control practices in coal mining operations.

Figure 3: Average particulate matter suspended in the air

These results highlight the effectiveness of various dust control measures for haul roads in open-cast coal mining operations, emphasizing the importance of proactive dust management strategies to mitigate environmental impact and enhance operational sustainability. The paper present the findings of the study, including the effectiveness of different dust control measures on haul roads in reducing dust emissions. efficiency in coal mining operations.

Conclusion: The importance of proactive dust management strategies for haul roads in open-cast coal mining to mitigate environmental impact and protect the well-being of workers and local communities. There is a need for continuous monitoring, innovation, and collaboration to achieve sustainable dust control practices in coal mining operations. Based on the data collected at location 1, 2, and 3, it is evident that the levels of particulate matter, particularly PM1, PM2.5, and PM10, vary significantly. In location 1, the concentrations are relatively lower compared to locations 2 and 3, where they are notably higher. These findings underscore the importance of continuous monitoring and assessment of dust pollution levels, especially in environments prone to high particulate matter emissions, such as mining sites.

The significant disparities in particulate matter concentrations emphasize the need for effective dust control measures and real-time monitoring solutions. The utilization of MEMS-sensor based personal dust samplers, as demonstrated in this study, presents a promising approach to address these challenges. By providing accurate and timely measurements of particulate matter levels, these devices enable proactive decision-making and intervention strategies to safeguard the health and well-being of workers in mining operations.

Furthermore, the integration of IoT technology and wireless communication facilitates seamless data transmission and analysis, enhancing the overall effectiveness of dust pollution management in mining environments. By harnessing the capabilities of these innovative solutions, stakeholders can work towards creating a safer and healthier working environment for mine workers, ultimately improving health outcomes and promoting sustainability within the mining industry

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